

Data on the Linkage Framework of Human Activity and Ecosystem Pressure in the Coastal Area of Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu UNESCO Global Geopark, Indonesia

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Abstract

One of the outcomes of Human Activity and Ecosystem Pressure in the Coastal Area of Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu UNESCO Global Geopark Research is a data linkage framework in the form of a matrix, which illustrates the relationships between sectors, activities, pressures, and affected ecosystems. This linkage framework is based on the Options for Delivering Ecosystem-Based Marine Management (ODEMM) Linkage Framework and supports decision-making and planning at Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu UNESCO Global Geopark (CPUGG), Indonesia. By connecting activities from various sectors to the environmental pressures they cause, this matrix facilitates the identification of sources of environmental pressure. This allows for the implementation of appropriate measures to mitigate these pressures. The matrix plays a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness of natural resource and environmental management efforts at CPUGG. It not only provides insights into the interconnections among sectors, pressures, activities, and impacted ecosystems but also supports systematic monitoring and policy management decisions. This matrix makes a significant contribution to integrating the analysis of human activities and environmental pressures at CPUGG.

Description

The dataset discussed in this report is in matrix form and is shown in Table 2, which is used to support the research by Taofiqurohman et al. (2024). This matrix is based on the ODEMM Linkage Framework, created and developed by White (1999) and Knight (2000). Furthermore, this matrix serves as a tool to understand the interactions between various human activities and the impacts they generate at CPUGG. By explicitly linking activities from different sectors to the corresponding environmental pressures, it becomes easy to identify sources of environmental pressure and take the necessary steps to address them. The data specifications are shown in table 1.

Table 1. Data specifications

Subject	: Decision Making
Area of Interest	: Ciletuh-Palabuhanratu UNESCO Global Geoparks, Indonesia.
Type of data	: Matrix
How data were acquired	: Survey and ODEMM Linkage Framework
Data format	: Analyzed

Value of the matrix

The matrix has several key uses in environmental management and activity planning:

- Environmental Impact Identification: This matrix aids in identifying the types of environmental impacts that could potentially occur from various activities at CPUGG.
- Decision-Making and Planning: Policymakers and planners for CPUGG can use information from the matrix to make more informed decisions regarding licensing, monitoring, and policies for the management of natural resources and the environment.
- Mitigation and Adaptation Priorities: The matrix helps determine the priorities for actions to mitigate and adapt to environmental impacts at CPUGG, focusing on activities that have the most 'linkages' or connections with environmental pressures.
- Risk Evaluation: By understanding the connections between activities and pressures, organizations and governments at CPUGG can better evaluate risks and prepare appropriate mitigation strategies.
- Cross-Sector Collaboration: This matrix facilitates dialogue and collaboration between various industrial sectors, government, and civil society in formulating solutions to complex environmental issues at CPUGG.

		Mooring/anchoring	X																	
		General					X	X	X											
		Running engine	X	X			X												X	
	Angling spot	Operational							X				X							
		Mooring/anchoring	X																	
		General							X	X										
		Running engine	X	X			X												X	
	Dive site	Operational	X						X				X							
Tourism		Mooring/anchoring	X																14	
		General							X	X										
	Public beach	General	X	X	X	X			X	X										
		Construction	X	X					X	X		X		X		X		X		
	Resort	Operational			X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X		X					
	Water sport	General	X	X			X	X	X										X	
	Total activity per pressure		17	19	6	7	7	4	12	16	23	3	1	5	2	5	9	1	12	2

Information :

- "X" represents the link between activity and pressure
- Amount* is the total type of pressure generated by a sector.

References

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